

NANNY ANNIE PROGRAM - NAP

AN ONGOING RESEARCH ON HOW TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF LIFE FOR CHILDREN WITH LEUKEMIA USING EMOTIONS AS A STARTING POINT

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ABSTRACT

Children suffering from leukemia (blood cancer) are often deprived of the usual activities in an ordinary child's life. The risks related to their condition and treatment drives parents and physicians to take the measurements needed to protect the child. Although the children's health is first priority in every case, their well-being involves other aspects such as emotional impact, that needs to be taken in account.

"To cure sometimes, to relieve often, to comfort always"; these are the guiding principles different doctors throughout their practice of medicine, and it serves as guideline for this particular project, which main purpose is improving the quality of life for children with leukemia, in means of comfort.

There is no eminent cure for cancer yet, but so far, the Nanny Annie Program (NAP) has designed three products that are aids for emotional and social well-being: the Dream Keeper, Annie-to-the-Rescue and Annie's Closet.

Keywords: childhood, cancer, quality of life, emotion and design

INTRODUCTION

It is a fact that when dealing with cancer it is impossible to find cure for every patient and it is no novelty that in pediatrics this truth turns difficult to cope with. But when facing the guidelines: "To cure sometimes, to relieve often, to comfort always", the possibility of optimizing life conditions for all patients, no matter their medical condition, appears as an

overriding factor for decision making regarding the life of a child.

So, whenever it is possible to intervene in an effort to favor the emotional, social, and psychological variables in the children's life, although it is important not to impair their health condition, it is indeed possible to offer the chance to grow among friends and family, play with them, and most important, bring a sense of childhood to a scene that is mainly difficult and filled with uncertainty.

There will always be a great concern regarding the threats that ordinary activities may present to a child with cancer. But maybe the answer is not to withdraw every chance of play, social encounters or even academic grounds, which are basic activities and environments in the life of a child. Cancer patients will always be at some risk of contracting an infection, yet children should not be deprived of the usual activities and variables that will help build their emotional and social abilities and eventually shape them as adults.

Studies that have been conducted in the United States show the underlying need that children and parents have towards having tools that could allow them to have a more ordinary life inside and outside the hospital. An evaluation made by different institutions in Boston to develop an Internet based system to support home management of childhood leukemia showed that parents are in a constant struggle to manage the complexity of their children's care at home. And when interviewing children directly, the lack of amusement, diversity and entertainment both at home and at the hospital was evident.

(Goldsmith, Silverman and Safran, 2002). This clear concern for guidance, that could aid or simplify home care for children with leukemia and maybe, be present also at the hospital, has been a factor that constantly appears in pediatric patients suffering different types of chronic disease.

Therefore, so far, the Nanny Annie Program (NAP, as we call it) features three complementary products that together work to physically protect the children from potential shocks, abrasions or cuts during play time; alert temperature changes in the body (fever); serve as company for hospitalization; and work as guide for parents and children to understand the illness, treatment, home care and other issues regarding cancer.

BACKGROUND

UNDERSTANDING THE PROBLEM

Cancer & Leukemia

Cells divide and replicate to form tissues, which in turn shape organs and systems, and all together constitute the human body. These cells carry the genetic information of each human being and it is where human systems' functions are coded. When a mutation occurs, either because of changes in the genetic code, a failure in the processes of cells, or a virus, endless division of a cell may cause malfunction of tissues, organs and the whole body system Purves, Sadava, Orians and Heller (2004). This type of condition is known as cancer and currently one in four deaths in the United States is due to cancer (Jamal, Siegel, Ward, Hao, Xu, Murray and Thun, 2008). Cancer cells grow out of control developing in abnormal size and shape tumors, they ignore their typical boundaries inside the body, destroy their neighbor tissues, and can ultimately spread (or metastasize) to other organs (Miller, 2007) causing a growing variety of problems.

Different kinds of cancer have different signs, symptoms, treatment, and outcomes, depending on the type of cells involved and the degree of uncontrolled cell growth (Miller, 2007). Leukemia constitutes approximately one-third of cancers in children (age 0–14 years), with Acute Lymphoblastic

Leukemia being the most frequent cancer in children (Coebergh, Reedijk, Vries, Martos, Jakab, Steliarova-Foucher and Kamps, 2006). In leukemia, blood cells are affected. These cells formed in the bone marrow consist of red cells, which carry oxygen to the tissues; platelets, which enable blood clotting and prevent abnormal bleeding; and white cells, which are the bases of the immune system and defend the body against infection (Travis, 1976). As normal functions of blood cells are compromised by leukemia, the patient suffers from anemia and fatigue due to the lack of red cells; coagulation deficit, bruises and abnormal bleeding or healing due to shortage of platelets; and infection propensity because of the malfunction of white cells (Boston Children's Hospital).

Treatment for leukemia is determined by physicians, and it differs depending on the patient, the risk factors, the evolution of the disease, and so on. Patients with more risk factors are generally treated more aggressively, and the treatment generally involves chemotherapy Semrud-Clikeman and Taller Ellison (2009). Drugs used are chemical poisons that damage or kill cells undergoing fast growth and replication (mostly cancer cells); but since drugs do not single out malignant cells, they can damage normal cells as well and their side effects are life threatening and highly distressing (Travis, 1976). Normal cells undergoing rapid growth may be damaged due to treatment and, in the case of leukemia, specific symptoms of the disease increase and sharpen because the same blood cells related to the disease are also affected by its treatment. Drugs aggravate, temporarily, the very hazards of the disease by lowering body defenses against infection (effect known as immunosuppression), and damaged clotting capacity of blood through platelet suppression (Miller, 2007). In consequence, patients often experience symptoms of the disease itself and side effects of the treatment (Viele, 2003).

RISKS & CONSEQUENCES

The subsequent deficits and risks that the disease and treatment lead, drives parents and physicians to take protective measurements for the child's sake. Certain activities and environments that may present a liability for the sake of the child's health are forbidden. Depending on health condition, the

progress of the treatment and the child's enduring of symptoms, restrictions around the child may change (either towards even more restraint or looseness). Adding hospital visits and stays to the sum of uncommon variables in a pediatric cancer patient makes it almost impossible for children to find normality in their unusual routine (Muñoz, 2009).

Because of the risks that children face when having leukemia, precautions have to be taken into account. It is important to understand that many variables are involved so the child's health condition may fluctuate (Muñoz, 2009) and that the child is not constantly facing undisputed danger.

Whenever white cells count is low, children are vulnerable to infections. This is a risk factor with a distinct level of alert. If a child presents fever higher than 38.5°C or constant 38°C for more than 4 hours, it is urgent to rush to the emergency room. Children with not enough defenses to fight infection are usually hospitalized with isolation measurements to provide a safe environment for them. Few people are allowed to get nearby, always abiding by sterilization recommendations.

On the other hand, platelets' function may be atypical so abnormal bleeding, bruises, hematomas and circulation or clotting deficiencies may determine changes in the rules of behavior and habituation. It may start with using a soft tooth-brush and go as far as banning any kind of sport, one-on-one games, or any other activity that may impact these factors (Muñoz, 2009).

Family and children emotional and social adaptation

Childhood cancer and its treatment pose a myriad of challenges for the child and family Semrud-Clikeman and Taller Ellison (2009). There was a time when cancer patients, especially children suffering from leukemia, had little chances of surviving. Despite the improved survival statistics, cancer remains a potentially life-threatening condition, and as such poses a major challenge for both child and family (Eiser, C., Eiser, J. and Stride, 2005). Although it is a relief for families to even have a chance for hope, facing a life threatening condition can be intensely

distressing for every family member. Family life as previously understood becomes disrupted and the child, parents, and other family members are confronted with a lengthy treatment regime and possible side effects (Eiser and Jenny, 2007).

The Jimmy Fund Clinic at the Dana-Farber Center Institute in Boston conducted a small study involving children and families to understand the management of home health care for patients. From the 25 parents that agreed to participate, 72% were mothers who stayed at home to take care of their child (Goldsmith, Silverman and Safran, 2002). Although the sample was small, it showed a family dynamic very common in families where a child suffers from a chronic illness. Mothers then appear to be at a higher risk for developing depression after treatment, possibly due to being most responsible for the daily care of the child Semrud-Clikeman and Taller Ellison (2009). Still, other family members such as the father, siblings and friends or close family are subjected to imperative changes because family dynamic is doomed to change.

In some hospitals and cancer centers, a multidisciplinary team is appointed to the family of the patient. The staff usually consists of nurses, doctors, social workers and psychologists. This team-directed approach serves to look after the family welfare in every angle ensuring their quality of life. The term quality of life (QoL) unifies many concerns that involve the idea of family member's well being. In health care, the concept often referred to as 'health related QoL' is generally understood as a multi-dimensional construct concerning an individual's perception of the impact of illness and treatment on his/her health, well-being or functioning in relation to physical, psychological, and social aspects of life (Savage, Riordan and Hughes 2009). This assessment of health-related quality of life has been increasingly recognized as providing an important marker of health outcome for children in the general population (Eiser and Jenny, 2007).

Given that children develop their basic socialization skills inside their family environment; and later on, relationships with friends and school mates continue to shape their character; it is important to understand that in order not to aggravate the situation, children should (whenever their health enables them) try to

establish or hold on to these relationships (Tovar, 2009).

It is clear that when facing the previously discussed threats, socialization in crowded environments such as school or participating in usual sports, games or playgrounds, there is constant exposure to risk factors. Some parents consider that for the sake of the child it is better to suspend school although it is not always the recommended action. Others (the minority) believe that school is an ordinary environment needed for the child's development. Either way, it is imperative to follow the physician and medical staff advices, especially regarding the health of the patient (Soler, 1996; Muñoz, 2009).

Furthermore, sometimes, emotional distress is even stronger in the hospital than at home or at school. Although currently more treatments have been developed that can be administered at home, (Goldsmith, Silverman and Safran, 2002) hospitalizations are still necessary, common, and sometimes traumatic. The level of comfort experienced in hospitals usually depends on several factors. For instance, the hospital infrastructure may provide patients and families a fair and suitable experience even in these circumstances. Some hospitals have playgrounds, libraries and Movie Theaters. The St. Louis Hospital at Missouri, as many other hospitals, has a siblings' playground that enables patients to have brothers and sisters visits in a safe recreational environment. There have been cases in which parents restrict siblings' interactions out of fear for the health condition of the sick child. This presents several problems for both siblings and family dynamics (Muñoz, 2009).

The medical staff may also be a factor that influences hospitals' experience. Some institutions' staff includes storytellers, musical therapists, teachers, and volunteers. Not every hospital offers these services and recreational environments, so life at the hospital is not always bearable.

Hospitalizations represent periods of time were children encounter a stop in their daily lives; but usually in cases of chronic illness in children, psychologist advocate for trying to continue with the

daily activities or at least daily routines to the possible extent (Tovar, 2009). Sleeping in beds other than their own, eating different food, not wearing their favorite clothes, not being accompanied by their whole family, felling alone, receiving constant medication, remaining connected to monitors and IVs at all times; these are only some of the usual conditions to endure in the hospital. No wonder the experience can be traumatic.

EMOTIONAL DESIGN STEPS IN

METHODOLOGY

The field research was conducted from February to October 2009 at the "Hospital Universitario Fundación Santa Fe". It began with 10 patients (3 girls, 7 boys) from 7 to 11 years. Their families (4 fathers, 8 mothers, 1 grandmother, 2 uncles and 2 sisters) were involved throughout the entire process. (In this proceeding the family member accompanying the child will be referred as guardian).

Patients were contacted personally in the presence of Dr. Muñoz, their oncologist, in the company of at least one guardian. Children and guardians were invited to different activities and interviews, both formal and informal. Because of the aim of the project and the characteristics of the sample, the study was conducted qualitatively and most of the research involved personal approach validated by the institution psychiatrist Dr. Maira Soto.

Direct communication was the principal method used to obtain the personal and specific version of the children experiences as well as their parents'. Early studies on health related quality of life in pediatric Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) tended to rely on reports by parents and health care professionals. More recently in pediatric studies in general, and pediatric ALL in particular, a number of studies have also asked children to complete questionnaires. In general, results indicate that by the age of 7 or 8 years, children generally provide reliable responses. Furthermore, a number of studies (Parsons, Barlow, Levy, Supran and Kaplan, 1999) indicate that children can often provide information that is unavailable through parental reports. Thus, children should be engaged as respondents whenever possible (Pickard, 2004). Accordingly, for this study, children were

addressed in friendly encounters to create familiar bonds that would allow them to feel free to talk about any worry, thought, need, lack, or discomfort; as well as wishes, hopes and dreams.

FROM THE CLINICAL EVIDENCE TO THE DESIGN STRATEGY

It is important to keep in mind that the children’s health was the priority in every case; still their well-being involves other aspects like emotional distress that were taken into account.

Recalling the main guideline of the project: “to cure sometimes, to relieve often, to comfort always”, a systematic classification was built tracing three possible clinical conditions in which the child may be situated (or fluctuating among). Specific variables characterize each condition so differentiation could be simple for children to understand and appropriate; this was extremely important so that children could give feedback on what they felt and thought in each stage (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Possible clinical conditions a child may face during illness. This classification is based on theoretical fundamentals but is subject to change after further research.

Starting from this characterization, a detailed series of events where constructed to synthesize the actions, environments, subjects and objects involved in the processes.

Figure 2 shows particular issues of Level 1. Not every step was relevant for the products presented but the structure and mapping of the experiences allows to understand the different variables that may be approached for new design proposals or other projects for NAP.

Figure 2. Time line of events as happen during hospitalization processes. Although the sequence is accurate, a series of other events may occur depending on each subject. This is a general overview to synthesize the process.

Later on, the different levels and the processes involved where analyzed with the medical staff, children and their families to discuss the possible concerns that could be present in each stage. The results provided a series of patterns regarding goals, attitudes and standards. Extended examples from Level 1 are shown (Figure 3). Levels 2 and 3 are only partially developed in this paper (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Concerns that children face when enduring Level 1 conditions. The list above considers some of the many thoughts expressed by children.

Figure 4. Concerns that children face when enduring Level 2 and 3 conditions. The list above considers some of the many thoughts that the children expressed.

TRANSFORMING THOUGHTS INTO PRODUCTS

Since the early 1980s, surviving cancer means not only achieving a clinical healthy state, but also a psychological, educational, and social condition Pizzo and Poplack (1898). One of the roads proposed in the project to accomplish this goal was to design tools that would allow children to achieve what they where lacking and, furthermore, improve their quality of life by focusing on emotional variables. Each level was deeply analyzed to find the best way to satisfy concerns without jeopardizing the children’s health.

Since the matter is mainly emotional, emotions and experiences were the starting point to develop solutions that would embrace as many issues as possible.

Insights where developed using Desmet’s appraisal model in order to analyze each situation with an emotional approach. An example of each level is provided (Figures 5, 5a and 5b).

The results shown are a synthesis of an extended exercise for each particular moment of the experiences related to each stage. These brief examples show some of the main points of interest that the study found relevant and from which further strategies where developed.

Figure 5. Level 1 emotions analysis following Desmet’s appraisal model (2002).

Figure 5a. Level 2 emotions analysis following Desmet’s appraisal model (2002).

Figure 5b. Level 3 emotions analysis following Desmet's appraisal model (2002).

Conceptualization

During the work with children it was impossible not to evoke memories from childhood. Piaget describes a reason why it is difficult for adults to understand children: We quickly forget what really means to be a child; we build vain and empty hopes of how children should be, and make assumptions of how we should have been when we ourselves were young. The lie relies in the fact that we cannot see what children really are because our expectations and memories of whom we use to be (Own translation from Labinowicz, 1998). So, in order for NAP to succeed in designing for children, they were invited to some conceptualization and brainstorming sessions.

For children and different researchers, quality of life has been associated with similar concepts such as health status or well-being; however, it also needs to stand for related psychological concepts such as happiness or optimism (Eiser and Jenny, 2007). Studies show how these emotional concepts are crucial for coping with the disease and treatment. Nevertheless, when facing distressing situation such as sickness, happiness and optimism are not easy to come by.

So conceptualization followed the words of Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi and Eugene Rochberg-Halton: The potential significance of things is realized in a process of actively cultivating a world of meanings, which both reflect and help create the ultimate goals of one's existence, Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981).

In this way, the work with children pointed to imagining a scenario in which circumstances were different, or more accurately: ideal. And then, picturing, mapping and designing the products that would at least try to enable the scenario to exist.

Different authors have described the daily experiences in such a way; objects serve as the set and props on the theatrical stage of our lives. They situate an individual's character or personality in a context (Goffman 1959; Holman 1980; Levy 1959; Mick 1986; Turner 1969; Wallendouf and Arnould, 1988). So for each level, a character was created: the adventurer, the explorer and the dreamer (Figure 6).

The process of creating the characters enabled the children to picture an imaginarium, or how we defined a recreation of a fantastic way of dealing with their issues. Due to their health disadvantages, they were encouraged to believe in the impossible when it came to abilities.

RESULTS

For each character, a product was designed accordingly to the concerns, stimuli and emotions previously discussed.

For the dreamer, the investigation was focused on favorite possessions and their importance during childhood. Research over the past 40 years has established that the attachment that infants and young children develop to certain soft, cuddly objects (e.g., blankets or teddy bears) serve important developmental functions. These objects are thought to symbolize the mother or certain characteristics of mothering in her absence by functioning as a source of comfort and security, and they appear to facilitate exploration of the social and physical environments. In addition, these objects are thought to foster

Imagination

**"Believe it hard enough and long enough...
and maybe it will appear before your eyes"**

Imagination is a human faculty that tends to manifest mostly during childhood. It is an ability to create, re create or dream and it is said that it feeds on what we know empirically. The more it is seen, the more it is heard and experimented, the more it is learned or absorbed and the more real elements one is aware of; that much more would imagination fly (Vigotsky, 2003).

1

A child in level 1 tends to be in critical health conditions and cannot to be in company of others. Isolation implies that visits are limited and given the parameters the child tend to feel lonely.

2

At level 2, although the children must remain in specific environments, unless their health condition demands it, they can interact with friends and family and engage on activities. Psychologist tend to recommend arts and crafts and literature or school homework to keep up with academic encouragement.

3

Children at level 3 are in conditions to go out, maybe play and be in the company of friends; at all time supervised by guardians or a responsible adult, following the physicians recommendations and understanding the boundaries to keep.

Dreamer

"I want someone to keep me company. Someone who never gets sick, never gets tired of being with me and doesn't mind spending entire weeks in the hospital."
Child

"I only like going to the hospital because I know I get to see Benja (friend with the same condition), but it's a bummer when I can't go outside the room."

Explorer

"I just don't like to get bored and sometimes I don't know how not to get bored."
Child

"The doctors and nurses know their part so well that sometimes I think they forget that we are new to this and don't anything. They know how to prescribe the medicines, but they can't help me get my child to take it when it tastes bad and she's nauseous anyway".
(Goldsmith, Silverman, Safran, 2002)

Adventurer

"I should be a superhero..."
Child

"Once she hit her head I we had to rush to the hospital because the bruises kept getting worst".
Mother

"If I knew he was going to be okay, then may be I'd let him play with his brother but I can't stand the though of him being hurt or something".
Mother

Dream keeper

**Annie to
the rescue**

Annie's Closet

Figure 6. Brief synthesis of the characters' origin for further conceptualization for each product

independence, individuation, persistence, and attention in young children (Kamptner, 1995; Winnicott, 1953; Myers 1985; Boniface and Graham, 1979).

The dream keeper, a toy companion for hospital stays, was created (Figure 7) and research around health and risk factors gave this product added value by using specific materials that would enable the child to keep the product at all times (hypoallergenic and

antibacterial textiles and stuffing). Furthermore, with textile and chemical technology, the dream keeper became more than a friend, a guardian. By cuddling with him, if the child's temperature increased, the dream keeper would change color. (Currently, different technological resources are being tested to corroborate the results and find the best solution to apply).

Figure 7. Sketch of the dream keepers. Textile technology and chemical compounds were used in order to achieve the thermal reaction to fever.

For the adventurer, in Level 3, a new brand of kids' clothing was developed (Annie's Closet), which purpose is to serve as protection system. What appears to be the ordinary daily attire is actually designed with a distinct purpose: to protect children from hits, strikes, scrapings, scratches and cuts in high impact areas: knees, elbows, wrists and head.

Finally, for the explorer, in level 2, the product is still being designed but it comprises: the corresponding instructions on how to take care of NAP products (dream keeper and adventurer's suit from Annie's closet), a series of recommended activities on how to spend time at the hospital or home and not get bored, advices from medical staff and cancer survivors and an A-Z dedicated to the illness, treatment and of what to expect during every stage, among other features. "Annie to the rescue" actually works to help with different issues, questions, concerns or simply advices for each stage of the disease.

Altogether, these products are being tested to corroborate results and measure their impact on children and families in means of their quality of life. This first research approach was done only with the pediatric oncology patients of Dr. Javier Muñoz, the physician who authorized the study. Although the sample for the study was small, the research done was extense and direct communication with children enabled a truthfully personal approach. Still, for further corroboration of results a larger sample of children joining the Nanny Annie Program is being assembled.

So far, amazing results have been shown in the way children interact with their dream keeper since it has managed to embody the characteristics of a companion with magical qualities, like changing colors when their owner gets sick (Figure 8).

On the other hand, both children and parents have shown a remarkable preference to the adventure's suit than to the usual clothing. Parents feel reassured and children confident. Besides, since the clothes do not have visible marks of protection and instead they look like ordinary clothing, children do not feel like wearing an armor suit with a sign of - be aware, I've got cancer -, a determinant that became evidently important during the study.

Figure 8. New appraisal model for Level 1.

Subsequent investigation is been undertaken in the fields of textile technology, children psychology and fashion trends in order to improve and innovate the products and simultaneously, the data is being revised to consolidate a compilation of important information that parents and children should have to finalize "Annie to the rescue."

Other variables are being considered like the possibility to personalize some of the products' features since it may increase the degree of attachment. By becoming self-expressive, the product may display the user identity (Mugge, Schiffersrein, Schoormans, 2004) and in the case of children this may reflect many affective states otherwise unperceivable for parents and physicians.

Over time, this review will be updated with new information as the Nanny Annie Program continues to work among children to improve their life quality.

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